

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates:
11 July – 20 August 2022

Report published: June 2023

Mountain ghosts: protecting snow leopards and other animals of the Tien Shan mountains of Kyrgyzstan

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Authors:

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**Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions**

Abstract

This study formed part of an ongoing annual citizen science expedition to the Tien Shan mountains in Kyrgyzstan. The expedition, organised by Biosphere Expeditions and NABU since 2014, takes place during the summer months, typically in July and August. Its main objective is to conduct surveys on the snow leopard (*Panthera uncia*) and its prey species. The methodology used involves volunteers and has been developed specifically for this purpose.

The 2022 survey area consisted of 76 cells, each measuring 2x2 km, at an average survey elevation of 3600 m (maximum 4000 m). Fifty-five percent of cells were sampled once, 45% of the cells were resampled twice or more, and 156 records of animals of interest were made in 62 cells. Previous expeditions had provided evidence suggesting the presence of snow leopards in the survey area. In 2022, as in previous years, nine purported signs of snow leopard presence were discovered (one camera trap photo, five scats and three tracks). Of the five scats, DNA analysis showed that only one was of snow leopard, three of red fox and one of a rodent. This shows how difficult it is to identify scats correctly. The other three purported signs were tracks and should be treated with extreme caution. In total two confirmed signs (one photo, one scat) were recorded during the expedition.

Two main groups of prey species were considered, i.e. primary (Siberian ibex *Capra sibirica* and argali *Ovis ammon*) and secondary (long-tailed or red marmot *Marmota caudata*, pika *Ochotona* sp., roe deer *Capreolus capreolus*, hare *Lepus tolai* and Himalayan snowcock *Tetraogallus himalayensis*). Siberian ibex comprised 38% of these records (including camera traps). Marmots were common at lower elevations (59%), whereas signs of Himalayan snowcock presence appeared at higher altitudes (mainly droppings left over from the winter season). Evidence of other carnivores sharing snow leopard habitat was also recorded. This included wolf (scats) and red fox (camera trap pictures). Foxes were found in several valleys; the wolf scat evidence was corroborated by herder testimony. Also captured on camera trap were badgers *Meles meles* twice, one stone marten *Martes foina* and one stoat *Mustela erminea*. It is noteworthy that, unlike in previous years, no signs of argali were found. An analysis of the data of the past four years has revealed a consistent and concerning decline in their population.

Finally, following on previous interview work, eleven local shepherds and their families were interviewed about eco-tourism and its potential for generating further income for local people.

It is clear that snow leopards are present in the Karakol river valley between the Karakol pass and Suusamy. It is interesting to note that captures are increasing year-by-year, but there is insufficient data to tell whether this is a positive sign connected to snow leopard presence increasing in the study area. It is also not known whether the animals recorded are one or more individuals, nor is anything else about their density, distribution and ecology known. This is because the expeditions have concentrated on a presence/absence study so far.

Previous prey-distribution modelling and the results of this expedition have shown that there is also a stable and healthy prey base that can and does support snow leopards in the study site. This does not include argali, however, who are in decline and were not recorded by the expedition in 2022 in a worrying trend.

Overgrazing is the most significant threat to snow leopards and other wildlife in the study area and this report details income sources other than livestock husbandry (ecotourism, community-based conservation, wildlife corridors) that could mitigate this threat. Interviews have shown that local herders are supportive of the idea. However, most herders are employed by larger livestock or land owners and it is unknown whether - and perhaps highly unlikely that - they would support a decrease in livestock numbers in the valley in favour of increased ecotourism and other activities. Further studies by a social science NGO are needed for this.

Eight years of expedition have shown there seems to be little appetite amongst them to prioritise the Karakol river valley between the Karakol pass and Suusamy for any kind of action in terms of protected area creation or community-based conservation initiatives through local tourism. This project in particular has attempted to create awareness and action for eight years and will do so for another year, in 2023, before considering moving elsewhere, where the limited resources of this citizen science endeavour are better placed and have higher chances of succeeding.

Резюме

Это исследование является частью ежегодной экспедиции гражданской науки в горы Тянь-Шань в Кыргызстане. Экспедиция, организованная Biosphere Expeditions и NABU с 2014 года, проводится в летние месяцы, обычно в июле и августе. Основная цель экспедиции - проведение исследований снежного барса (*Panthera uncia*) и его добычи. Методология, используемая в данном исследовании, предполагает использование волонтеров и была специально разработана для этой цели.

Территория исследований 2022 года состояла из 76 ячеек, каждая из которых имела размеры 2x2 км, средняя высота исследуемых участков составляла 3600 м (максимум 4000 м). Пятьдесят пять процентов ячеек были проверены один раз, 45% ячеек были повторно проверены дважды или более, и было зарегистрировано 156 наблюдений интересующих животных в 62 ячейках. Предыдущие экспедиции предоставили доказательства наличия снежных барсов на исследуемой территории. Как и в предыдущие годы, в 2022 году было обнаружено девять предполагаемых признаков присутствия снежного барса (одно фото с камеры-ловушки, пять экскрементов и три следа). Из пяти экскрементов ДНК-анализ показал, что только один принадлежит снежному барсу, три - красной лисице, а один - грызуну. Это показывает, как трудно правильно идентифицировать экскременты. Другие три предполагаемых признака были следами и должны быть рассмотрены с большой осторожностью. Всего было зафиксировано два подтвержденных признака (одно фото, один экскремент) во время экспедиции.

Были рассмотрены две группы видов добычи т.е. как основные: первичные (сибирский горный козел *Capra sibirica* и горный баран *Ovis ammon*) и вторичные (длиннохвостый или красный сурок *Marmota caudata*, пищуха *Ochotona sp.*, косуля *Capreolus capreolus*, заяц *Lepus tolai* Pall. и гималайский улар *Tetraogallus himalayensis*). Сибирский горный козел составлял 38% от общего числа наблюдений (включая фото с камер-ловушек). Сурки были распространены на низменностях (59%), в то время как признаки присутствия гималайского улара наблюдались на более высоких высотах (в основном это были остатки его отходов от зимнего сезона). Были также зарегистрированы признаки наличия других хищников, разделяющих места обитания снежного барса. Это включало волков (экскременты) и красных лисиц (фотографии с камер-ловушек). Лисицы были обнаружены в нескольких долинах, а наличие волчьих экскрементов было подтверждено показаниями пастухов. На фото с камер-ловушек также были запечатлены барсуки, дважды *Meles meles*, одна каменная куница *Martes foina* и один горноста *Mustela erminea*. Следует отметить, что, в отличие от предыдущих лет, признаков горного барана не было найдено. Анализ данных последних четырех лет показал последовательное и тревожное снижение их популяции.

Наконец, в продолжение предыдущих интервью было проведено интервью с одиннадцатью местными пастухами и их семьями о экотуризме и его потенциале для создания дополнительного дохода для местного населения.

Понятно, что снежные барсы присутствуют в долине реки Каракол между перевалом Каракол и Суусамыр. Интересно отметить, что количество фиксаций увеличивается из года в год, но данных недостаточно, чтобы сказать, является ли это положительным признаком увеличения численности снежных барсов в исследуемой области. Также неизвестно, являются ли зафиксированные животные одним или несколькими особями, а также ничего неизвестно о их плотности, распределении и экологии. Это связано с тем, что экспедиции до сих пор сосредотачивались на изучении наличия или отсутствия снежных барсов.

Предыдущая моделирование распределения добычи и результаты этой экспедиции показали, что также существует стабильная и здоровая популяция добычи, способная поддерживать снежных барсов на исследуемой территории. Однако это не включает горного барана, которые находятся на упадке и не были зафиксированы экспедицией в 2022 году, что является тревожной тенденцией.

Чрезмерный выпас является наиболее значительной угрозой для снежных барсов и других диких животных в исследуемой области, и в данном отчете описываются источники дохода, отличные от скотоводства (экотуризм, организация охраны с участием местного населения, коридоры для диких животных), которые могут смягчить эту угрозу. Интервью показали, что местные пастухи поддерживают эту идею. Однако большинство пастухов работают на крупных владельцев скота и неизвестно, будут ли они поддерживать сокращение численности скота в долине в пользу развития экотуризма и других активностей. Для этого требуются дополнительные исследования от неправительственной организации в этой области.

К сожалению, восьмилетний опыт экспедиции показывает, что существует малая заинтересованность среди местного населения в вопросах создания охраняемой территории или инициатив по охране с участием местного сообщества через туризм в долине реки Каракол между перевалом Каракол и Суусамыр. Этот проект, в частности, пытается привлечь внимание и сподвигнуть к действиям в течение восьми лет и будет продолжать это делать еще один год, в 2023 году, прежде чем рассмотреть возможность переезда в другую область, где ограниченные ресурсы этой гражданской научной экспедиции могут быть лучше использованы и имеют больше шансов на успех.

Корутунду

Бул изилдөө Кыргызстандын Тянь-Шань тоолорунда жыл сайын өтүүчү жарандык илимий экспедициянын бир бөлүгү. 2014-жылдан бери Biosphere Expeditions жана NABU тарабынан уюштурулган экспедиция жай мезгилде, адатта июль жана август айларында өтөт. Экспедициянын негизги максаты ак илбирсти (*Panthera uncia*) жана анын олжосун изилдөө. Бул изилдөөдө колдонулган ыкма ыктыярчыларды колдонууну камтыйт жана бул максат үчүн атайын иштелип чыккан.

Изилдөө аянты 2022-жылы 76 уячалардан турган, алардын ар биринин өлчөмү 2x2 км барабар, изилденген аймактардын орточо бийиктиги 3600 м (максималдуу 4000 м) болгон. Уячалардын 55 пайызы бир жолу текшерилген, уячалардын 45 пайызы эки же андан көп жолу текшерилген жана 62 уячада максат кылынган жаныбарлардын 156 байкоосу катталган. Буга чейинки экспедициялар изилденип жаткан аймакта ак илбирстердин бар экенин далилдешкен. Өткөн жылдардагыдай эле, 2022-жылы илбирстин бар экенине себепкер боло турган тогуз белги табылган (капкан-камерадан бир сүрөт, беш заң жана үч изи). Беш заңдын ДНК анализи көрсөткөндөй, бирөө гана ак илбирске, үчөө кызыл түлкүгө, бирөө кемирүүчүгө таандык экени билинген. Бул заңдын туура аныктоо канчалык кыйын экенин көрсөтүп турат. Калган үч сунушталган белгилер издер болгон жана өтө кылдаттык менен каралышы керек. Экспедиция учурунда бардыгы болуп эки тастыкталган белги (бир сүрөт, бир заң) аныкталган.

Жырткыч түрлөрүнүн эки тобу каралып, б.а. негизги катары: биринчилик (кадимки тоотекке *Capra sibirica* жана аркар *Ovis ammon*) жана экинчилик (узун куйруктуу же кызыл суур *Marmota caudata*, коен чычкан *Ochotona* sp., элик *Capreolus capreolus*, коён *Lepus tolai* Pall. жана гималай улары *Tetraogallus himalayensis*). Кадимки тоотекке көргөндөрдүн жалпы санынын 38% түзгөн (капкан-камералардан алынган сүрөттөрдү кошкондо). Суурлар төмөн жерлерде кеңири таралган (59%), ал эми гималай улар бар экендигинин белгилери бийик жерлерде байкалган (негизинен анын кыш мезгилиндеги калдыктарынын ийзери). Ак илбирс менен жашаган башка жырткычтардын да белгилери байкалган. Буга карышкырлар (заң) жана кызыл түлкүлөр (капкан-камера сүрөттөрү) кирген. Бир нече өрөөндөрдө түлкүлөр табылып, карышкырдын заңы бар экенин чабандардын көрсөтмөлөрү менен тастыкталган. Капкан-камералардын сүрөттөрүнө кашулак, эки жолу *Meles meles*, бир таш суусар *Martes foina* жана бир арс чычкан *Mustela erminea* да тартылган. Белгилей кетсек, өткөн жылдардан айырмаланып, аркар белгилери табылган эмес. Акыркы төрт жылдын маалыматтарын талдоосунун негизинде, алардын санынын ырааттуу жана коркунучтуу азайгандыгын көрсөттү.

Андан сырткары, мурунку сурамжылоолорго кошумча, он бир жергиликтүү малчы жана алардын үй-бүлөлөрү менен экотуризм жана анын жергиликтүү калк үчүн кошумча киреше алуу потенциалы тууралуу сурамжылоо өткөрүлдү.

Каракол ашуусу менен Суусамырдын ортосундагы Каракол дарыясынын өрөөнүндө ак илбирстер бар экени анык. Кызыгы, байкалган белгилердин саны жылдан жылга көбөйүп жатат, бирок бул изилденүүчү аймакта ак илбирстердин санынын көбөйүшүнүн оң белгиси деп айтууга маалыматтар жетишсиз. Ошондой эле катталган жаныбарлардын жеке жалгыз организм же бир нече экендиги белгисиз андан сырткары, алардын тыгыздыгы, таралышы жана экологиясы тууралуу эч нерсе белгилүү эмес. Себеби, экспедициялар буга чейин ак илбирстин бар же жок экенин гана изилдөөгө басым жасап келишкен.

Чабыттын мурунку бөлүштүрүлүшүн моделдөө жана бул экспедициянын натыйжалары, ошондой эле изилденүүчү аймакта ак илбирс жашоого жөндөмдүү туруктуу чабыт популяциясы бар экенин көрсөттү. Бирок 2022-жылы экспедиция учурунда катталбай калган аркарлар бул жыйынтыкка киришпейт жана кооптондуруу тенденциясын жаратат.

Ашыкча мал жаюу – бул изилдөөчү аймактагы ак илбирстерге жана башка жапайы жаныбарларга эң олуттуу коркунуч. Бул маалымат аталган коркунучтуу басандата турган малчылыктан (экотуризм, коомчулукту коргоо, жапайы жаратылыш чубамалар) башка киреше булактарын сунуштайт. Бул элести жергиликтүү чабандар да колдой тургандыктарын сурамжылоолор көрсөттү. Бирок малчылардын көбү ири мал ээлери үчүн иштешет жана алар экотуризмди өнүктүрүү жана башка иш-чаралардын пайдасына өрөөндө малдын санын кыскартууну колдойбу же жокпу белгисиз. Бул үчүн бейөкмөт уюмдар бул багытта көбүрөөк изилдөө жүргүзүшү керек.

Тилекке каршы, экспедициянын сегиз жылдык тажрыйбасы көрсөткөндөй, Каракол ашуусу менен Суусамырдын ортосундагы Каракол дарыясынын өрөөнүндө туризм аркылуу, жергиликтүү коомчулуктун катышуусу менен өзгөчө корголуучу аймакты түзүүгө же жаратылышты коргоо демилгесин колдоого жергиликтүү калктын кызыгуусу төмөн. Бул долбоор сегиз жыл бою аталган көйгөйгө көңүл бурууну жана кандайдыр бир иш-аракеттерди жаратууга аракет кылып келген жана бул жарандык илимий экспедициянын чектелген ресурстары жакшыраак колдонула турган башка аймакка көчүүнү кароодон мурун, 2023-жылы дагы бир ирээт аракетин көрөт.

Contents

Abstract	2
Резюме	3
Корутунду	4
Contents	5

1. Expedition Review	6
1.1. Background	6
1.2. Dates & team	6
1.3. Partners	7
1.4. Acknowledgements	7
1.5. Further information & enquiries	8
1.6. Expedition budget	8

2. Monitoring snow leopards and other species...	9
2.1. Introduction	9
2.2. Materials & methods	9
2.3. Results	11
2.4. Discussion & conclusions	21
2.5. Literature cited	24

Appendix I: Mammal sightings and call records of the 2022 expedition	25
Appendix II: Mammal and bird sign records of the 2022 expedition.	26
Appendix III: Expedition reports, publications, diary etc	27

1. Expedition Review

M. Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

Background information, location conditions and the research area are as per [Tytar et al. \(2019c\)](#). The aim of the expedition was to survey for snow leopard *Panthera uncia* and its prey species.

1.2. Dates & team

The project ran over a period of six weeks divided into three 13-day group rotations, each composed of a team of national and international citizen scientists, a professional scientist and an expedition leader. Group dates were as shown in the team list below.

The expedition team was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

11 – 23 July 2022

Lydia Azarina (Korea), Jörg Dutz (Germany), Anke Hoffmann (Germany), Colleen Krog (South Africa), Alan Lee (UK), Valerie Ní Fhlaithearta (Belgium), Anne Otto (Germany), Kubanychek Tagaibekov* (Kyrgyzstan), Jason Tempelton (UK), Pierre Villard (France), Nadine Zimmann (Czech Republic).

25 July – 6 August 2022

Francesco Bellezza-Quater (Italy), Anna Dudek (Germany), Kathy Haan*+ (USA), Margot Knuth (USA), Georg Kuales (Germany), Sylvain Masse (Switzerland), Felix Maßem (Germany), Martina Suhm (Germany).

8 – 20 August 2022

Wendy Astill (UK), Ria Bleich (Germany), Simone Galavazi (Netherlands), Irving Hellwig (Germany), Haley Hendrix (USA), Lars Hildebrandt (Germany), Sarah Macharg (UK), Walter Macharg (UK), Karin Spevak (Austria), Roland Thielbeer (Germany), Christine Tivenan (UK).

*local placement (sponsored by the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions) | +press

Also, our expedition cook throughout the expedition, Gulia Subanova and ranger Aman Talgartbekov and, on a rotational basis, members of NABU's anti-poaching patrol Grupa Bars: Zhyrgalbek Sultanov, Zhenisch Tursuniasov, Ayan Dosjanov and Bekbolot Ozgorush Uulu, all from Kyrgyzstan.

A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place. There was one incidence of an eye infection, which had to be treated at a local clinic. There were also several Covid cases, which were all effectively managed by the Covid procedures in place.

The expedition scientist was Taalai Mambetov, a Kyrgyz national with a Master's degree from the Faculty of Biology, Kyrgyz National University named after Jusup Balasagyn. He began his scientific career as a junior researcher at the National Academy of Sciences. Since 2017, he is a teacher and field biologist at his alma mater. Taalai has participated in various projects (ICBA, FFI, Kew Botanical Garden project etc.), mainly related to biodiversity.

The first group of the expedition was led by Malika Fettak. Malika is half Algerian, but was born and educated in Germany. She majored in Marketing & Communications and worked for more than a decade in both the creative department, but also in PR & marketing of a publishing company. Her love of nature, travelling and the outdoors (and taking part in a couple of Biosphere expeditions) showed her that a change of direction was in order. Joining Biosphere Expeditions in 2008, she runs the German-speaking operations and the German office and leads expeditions all over the world whenever she can. She has travelled extensively, is multilingual, a qualified off-road driver, diver, outdoor first aider, and a keen sportswoman.

The rest of the expedition was led by Roland Arnison. Roland studied Environmental Science and is a qualified Mountain Leader, a Mountain Rescue volunteer and has led a variety of expeditions in the UK, Canada, Iceland and Namibia, including introducing young people to the joys and challenges of expeditions in wild places. He has run expedition citizen science projects ranging from sampling for plastic pollution in the ocean to searching for the elusive Collared Pika in the Yukon as a bio-indicator of climate change. Roland's mountaineering exploits have taken him to un-climbed peaks in the Himalayas and equally challenging times in the Scottish hills in winter. Roland enjoys kayaking, climbing, cycling, filming, photographing, diving and sometimes just walking in some wonderful and wild parts of the world. He has also spent many years looking after a smallholding in Yorkshire, creating wildlife habitats, and experimenting with novel food growing and renewable energy projects.

1.3. Partners

[NABU](#) (= Naturschutzbund = nature protection alliance), founded in 1899, is one of Germany's oldest and its biggest conservation NGOs. In Kyrgyzstan, NABU, in cooperation with the Kyrgyz government, is implementing a programme to conserve the snow leopard through a twin approach of research and the prevention of illegal hunting and trade of the endangered species (see <http://nabu.kg/wp/>).

1.4. Acknowledgements

We are grateful to the expedition participants, who not only dedicated their spare time to helping but also, through their expedition contributions, funded the research. Thank you also to our partner organization NABU, in particular NABU's Gruppa Bars. Thank you also to Almaz Alzhambaev of www.carforrent.kg, the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions and all donors to a fundraising campaign for their support. Finally, thank you to the peer reviewers for helpful comments.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

Enquiries should be addressed to Biosphere Expeditions at the address given on the website.

1.6. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist participant paid towards expedition costs a contribution of € 2,780 per person per 13-day group. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special research equipment and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	93,753
Expenditure	
Expedition base includes all food & services	13,330
Transport includes hire cars, fuel, taxis in Kyrgyzstan	11,387
Equipment and hardware includes research materials & gear etc. purchased internationally & locally	14,760
Staff includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff salaries and travel expenses	17,058
Administration includes miscellaneous fees & sundries	3,773
Team recruitment Tien Shan as estimated % of annual PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	4,630
Income – Expenditure	28,815
Total percentage spent directly on project	69%

2. Monitoring snow leopards and other species on the south side of the Kyrgyz Ala-Too mountain range in the Tien Shan mountains of Kyrgyzstan

Taalai Mambetov
Jusup Balasagyn Kyrgyz National University

2.1. Introduction

The snow leopard (*Panthera uncia*) is an endangered species found in central Asia. Its biology, distribution and its situation in Kyrgyzstan is described in [Tytar & Hammer 2015](#), [Tytar et al. 2016](#), [Tytar et al. 2017](#), [Tytar et al. 2018](#), [Tytar et al. 2019c](#).

The main aim of this expedition, running since 2014, was to determine if the species was present in the Kyrgyz Ala-Too mountains and evaluate the potential prey base. Specific aims of the 2022 expedition were to:

1. Continue to evaluate and map - via citizen science and community monitoring efforts - the current status of snow leopard populations in the Kyrgyz Ala-Too range, concentrating efforts in areas predicted to have good habitat suitability for both the snow leopard and its prey.
2. Introduce DNA-based scat analysis methodology to elucidate how many individuals are present in the Kyrgyz Ala-Too range.
3. Conduct interviews with local people on nature conservation issues, particularly on their vision of how the area could be protected and the role of the local community.
4. Continue to develop relationships with local partner NABU and the Kyrgyz Ala-Too local community in order to further community-based conservation activities and the creation of a community-based NGO and protected area.

2.2. Materials and methods

Kyrgyz Ala-Too study site

The Kyrgyz Ala-Too study site and the rationale for running the expedition there are described in Tytar & Hammer 2015, Tytar et al. 2016, Tytar et al. 2017, Tytar et al. 2018, Tytar et al. 2019c.

The 2022 base camp was located close to the Suusamyr-Kochkor road approximately in the middle of the chosen study area (N 42.359386°, E 74.740734°). From base camp one-day surveys were conducted in the Kyrgyz Ala-Too mountain range, with side valleys reached by car and further investigated on foot.

Methods & training of citizen scientist participants

Methods employed, sampling and data analysis techniques, as well as the training of international and local citizen scientist participants were as described in Tytar & Hammer 2015, Tytar et al. 2016, Tytar et al. 2017, Tytar et al. 2018, Tytar et al. 2019c.

In addition, in 2022 scat was collected for DNA analysis following the [Snow Leopard Conservancy / Texas A&M University DNA sampling protocol](#).

Twenty-six camera traps were installed and maintained in the study between 14 July and 15 August 2022. Two strategies were employed to install the cameras: subjective site selection by the expedition team and in line with the species distribution model built on previously obtained visual records of Siberian ibex, the main food source for the snow leopard (Tytar et al. 2019a).

After the expedition, these camera traps are maintained by the community monitoring group set up in previous years by the expedition (Tytar et al. 2016, Tytar et al. 2017, Tytar et al. 2018, Tytar et al. 2019c) through the winter of 2022/2023 up to the arrival of the next expedition.

A prey base survey was also conducted in line with the methods cited above. Two main groups of prey species were considered, i.e. primary (Siberian ibex *Capra sibirica* and argali *Ovis ammon*) and secondary (long-tailed or red marmot *Marmota caudata*, pika *Ochotona* sp., roe deer *Capreolus capreolus*, hare *Lepus tolai* and Himalayan snowcock *Tetraogallus himalayensis*). Evidence of other carnivores (wolf, fox) sharing snow leopard habitat was also recorded.

Camera traps were employed during the expedition by citizen scientists and maintained by the community monitoring group through the winter of 2022/2023 up to the arrival of the next expedition.

Finally, following on from interviews conducted during previous expeditions (Tytar et al. 2017, Tytar et al. 2018, Tytar et al. 2019c, Tytar et al. 2022), the 2022 expedition interviewed eleven local shepherds and their families about eco-tourism and its potential for generating further income for local people (Fig 2.3j).

The interview leitmotif was to ascertain whether herders have the ability and motivation of organizing ecotourism activities in the valley of the Karakol river and see this as a viable source of additional income.

Questions asked were:

- > Do you have the resources to host adventure tourists in the valley? If so, what would that look like? Someone pitching a tent nearby? Or someone staying in your yurt? Can you feed them traditional foods?
- > Can you show tourists the elements of a yurt, or how to make traditional dairy products such as koumiss and kurut?

- > Do you know any traditional songs you can teach tourists? Can you play traditional instruments? What about teaching them traditional games?
- > Can you organize an ulak tartysh game?

2.3. Results

Animal surveys

Seventy-six cells, each 2x2 km in size, located in the southern Kyrgyz Ala-Too mountain range were surveyed for snow leopard and other vertebrates, including small, medium and large-sized mammals and game birds. Surveys were conducted at an average elevation of 3600 m, the highest surveyed elevation was 4000 m. Individual survey groups included three to four citizen scientists and daily efforts comprised six to ten hours, depending in most cases on weather conditions, distance of the survey from base camp and complexity of the terrain. Fifty-five percent of cells were sampled once, 45% of the cells were resampled twice or more, and 156 records of animals of interest were made in 62 cells.

Nine purported signs of snow leopard presence were found during the expedition: one camera trap photo, five scats and three tracks. Of the five scats, DNA analysis showed that only one was of snow leopard, Figs 2.3c, 2.3d (collected 1 August 2022 at 3800 m in cell AF15), three of red fox and one of a rodent. This shows how difficult it is to identify scats correctly. The other three purported signs were tracks and should be treated with extreme caution Fig 2.3e, 2.3f. In total two confirmed signs (one photo, one scat) were recorded during the expedition (Table 2.3a).

Camera traps during the expedition photographed snow leopard once Fig 2.3a, fox twice, ibex eight times, marmots five times and snowcock 15 times. The community camera trap monitoring group (CCTMG) continued monitoring by camera trap throughout the pandemic, when expeditions with international citizen scientists were not possible. The CCTMG installed 12 camera traps throughout the study site before the 2022 expedition and again 15 camera traps after the 2022 expedition. As reported in Tytar et al. (2022), several very clear snow leopard pictures were captured in one location in September 2021 (Fig. 2.3b) and later again in another. SD cards from the camera traps set after the 2022 expedition have not been retrieved at the time of writing.

Snow leopard records obtained during the 2022 expedition are summarized in Table 2.3a (exact locations are omitted for conservation reasons).

Table 2.3a. Snow leopard signs recorded by the 2022 expedition.

Date	Elevation (m)	Type of record	Figure
1 August 2022	3800	Scat on gravel	
9 August 2022	3800	Camera trap pictures	2.3a

Figure 2.3c. Scat amongst rocks, 18 July 2022.
DNA analysis showed that this was not of snow leopard.

Figure 2.3d. Scat with bone, 29 July 2022.
DNA analysis showed that this was not of snow leopard.

Figure 2.3e. Track in gravel, 12 August 2022.
This was not scored as snow leopard for lack of corroborating evidence.

Figure 2.3f. Track in sand, 12 August 2022.
This was not scored as snow leopard for lack of corroborating evidence

Figure 2.3a. One of a series of camera trap pictures of a snow leopard individual, photographed on 9 August 2022.

Figure 2.3b. One of a series of camera trap pictures of a snow leopard individual, photographed in September 2021.

Signs of snow leopard prey species collected during the expedition during presence/absence surveys were found to be fairly abundant and widespread in a variety of terrains (156 records). A summary is given in Fig 2.3g and Table 2.3i, and individual records are in appendices I and II. Siberian ibex comprised 37% of these records (including camera traps). Marmots were common at lower elevations (59%) Fig 2.3h, whereas signs of Himalayan snowcock presence appeared at higher altitudes, Fig 2.3j (these indications were mainly droppings left over from the winter season).

It is noteworthy that, unlike in previous years, no signs of argali were found. An analysis of the data of the past four years has revealed a consistent and concerning decline in their population.

Figure 2.3g. Total number and percentage records of prey species.

Figure 2.3h. Ibex (top) and marmot spotted during surveys.

Upon analysing the gathered data from the expedition, including data from camera traps, we have identified a significant presence of Siberian ibex, which serves as a crucial prey species for the snow leopard. Additionally, numerous other prey species were also documented during the expedition. A summary of findings is in Table 2.3i. Detailed sign findings are in Appendices I and II.

Table 2.3i. Indication of snow leopard prey animals.

Animal	No of animals sighted	Sign found in cells	Avg. percent of indication rate*		
			Sighting	Scats	Tracks
Siberian ibex	51	AE 21, AB 19, AG 14, AG 15, AF 21, AH 20	36%	55%	55%
Marmot	98	AE 17, AE 19, AE 20, AF 19, AF 20, AG 18, AG 19, AG 16, AI 18, AE 18, AI 17	66%	50%	50%
Snowcock	2	AE 16, AE 17, Z 17, Z 16, AJ 19, AF 15, AE 15, AA 20, AD 18	10%	60%	30%

*Indicates likelihood of finding evidence (including camera trap data, scats and tracks).

Note that Table 2.3i contains various signs such as "Sighting," "Scats," and "Tracks", which account for a total of 98 observations. The table specifically focuses on snow leopard prey, excluding animals such as foxes and badgers and therefore does not show the category "Other". Figure 2.3g in the chart represents "Sighting" and "Call" occurrences without considering tracks and scats, with a count of 92 instances.

Figure 2.3j Snowcocks captured on camera trap.

Evidence of other carnivores sharing snow leopard habitat was also recorded. This included wolf *Canis lupus* (scats) and red fox *Vulpes vulpes* (camera trap pictures). Foxes were found in several valleys; the wolf scat evidence was corroborated by herder testimony. Wolves are the major predators in the area, causing losses to domestic livestock, therefore arousing deep concern amongst herders. Herders reported at least two cases when wolves had attacked the livestock.

Also captured on camera trap were badgers *Meles meles* twice, one stone marten *Martes foina* and one stoat *Mustela erminea*. It is worth noting that the weasel is listed in the Red Data Book of Kyrgyzstan under the VII category (lower risk and least concern LR/LC for its conservation status).

Interviews

Most of the interviewed herders met the idea of ecotourism providing additional income positively and enthusiastically, Fig 2.3k. Common answers provided were:

- > We can install an additional yurt especially for tourists. We know how to cook various dishes. If we are required to do something special or new, we are open to discussion.
- > No doubt, we can show visitors how to prepare our national dairy products, including kurut, kaimak etc. We can also explain how to erect a yurt. Also, we know the valley and can arrange horse riding to special places (such as petroglyph stones).
- > We can arrange a *ulak tartysh* (goat pulling game) between herders of upper vs lower valley teams easily (once a week).

Figure 2.3k. Interviewing a local herder family.

Herder families also asked specific questions back. These included:

- > How many visitors would be interested in coming?
- > What will be provided by the organizers?
- > How long will this project work?

2.4. Discussion and conclusions

Snow leopards and their prey are present in the Karakol valley

It is clear that snow leopards are present in the Karakol river valley between the Karakol pass and Suusamyr. Anecdotal evidence from local people in 2014 (Tytar & Hammer 2015) indicated that snow leopard was present in the area and confirmed the importance of the study area as a habitat for snow leopard. Subsequent sign surveys (Tytar et al. 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019c, 2020, 2022) yielded further confirmation of snow leopard presence by discovering a multitude of snow leopard signs, as well as camera-trapping individuals on multiple and regular occasions since 2019. It is interesting to note that captures are increasing year-by-year, but there is insufficient data to tell whether this is a positive sign connected to snow leopard presence increasing in the study area. It is also not known whether the animals recorded are one or more individuals, nor is anything else about their density, distribution and ecology known. This is because the expeditions have concentrated on a presence/absence study so far.

Prey-distribution modelling (Tytar et al. 2018, 2019c, 2020, 2022) and the results of this expedition have shown that there is also a stable and healthy prey base that can and does support snow leopards in the study site. This does not include argali, however, who are in decline and were not recorded by the expedition in 2022 in a worrying trend.

Livestock (over)grazing a real threat to snow leopard and prey survival

With the current post-socialist era growth of the human population in the country in general and in the study site in particular, competition for pasture grounds and development may nullify positive snow leopard and prey base trends documented by the expeditions since they started in 2014, and drive the snow leopard and its prey out of the area. The 2022 expedition in particular observed a significant increase in the amount of livestock in the area (and perhaps a concomitant decrease in argali numbers), as well as the absence of any policing of livestock numbers, which in theory should be regulated. It is common knowledge, however, that livestock numbers are significantly higher than official numbers due to the direct economic benefits for herd owners, coupled with a lack of effective policing of the permit system.

Animal husbandry serves as the primary source of income for numerous families residing in mountainous regions, especially in areas where farming is challenging or impractical. The Karakol river valley, categorised as a winter pasture, is accessible only during a short period in summer. The allocation of pastures is managed by the pasture committee in each rural aimak (district), which issues pasture tickets based on livestock numbers. Herders pay an

annual fee corresponding to their livestock count and receive the appropriate grazing land. However, a significant challenge arises due to the substantial number of farmers, even more livestock, and limited land availability. Consequently, there is an excess of animals occupying land that cannot adequately sustain them. Yaks are of particular concern since other domestic animals such as cows, sheep, and horses vacate these areas before the arrival of cold weather, allowing the land to rest and regenerate. Yaks, on the other hand, are semi-wild creatures that remain in the mountains throughout the year, consuming grass and causing notable damage to the soil structure. In recent years, there has been an alarming upward trend in the population of yaks, including in the Karakol river valley. This situation further exacerbates the already challenging circumstances in the area and imposes unprecedented pressure on wildlife.

Income sources other than livestock husbandry: ecotourism and community-based conservation

One mitigating approach to addressing the challenge of overgrazing livestock in the Karakol valley could be the implementation of community-based conservation initiatives that generate income through ecotourism. These initiatives involve local communities actively participating in the conservation and management of their natural resources, while also benefiting economically from sustainable tourism practices. By promoting ecotourism activities, such as for example guided wildlife tours, nature-based excursions and cultural experiences, communities can diversify their sources of income and reduce their reliance on livestock grazing alone. This would not only alleviate pressure on the pastures, but also create incentives for local residents to actively protect and preserve their natural environment.

Seventy percent of the shepherds interviewed by the expedition expressed their willingness to consider a complete transition to alternative income sources, if it could rival or come close to their main earnings. There is, however, some understandable hesitancy to embark on new ventures, because herders fear the unknown and have limited experience in such endeavours. An additional challenge is that interviews have shown that most herders are employed by larger livestock or land owners and it is unknown whether – and perhaps highly unlikely that – they would support a decrease in livestock numbers in the valley in favour of increased ecotourism and other activities as proposed above. This, amongst other issues in social science, needs further study, which Biosphere Expeditions – as a wildlife conservation organisation, rather than a social science NGO – is not equipped to do on a professional level, so it would need other, more qualified organisations to pick up the baton.

Wildlife corridors instead of nature reserves?

An alternative approach to conserving and protecting wild animals in the region could be the establishment of wildlife corridors instead of traditional nature reserves. These corridors could serve as pathways for the unrestricted movement of wildlife, facilitating biodiversity conservation while mitigating potential conflicts with the livelihoods of herders and local communities.

Implementation and local lack of appetite for action and what this means for the expedition

Of course, all of these efforts have to be implemented and require collaboration between government agencies, local communities and relevant stakeholders to monitor and enforce compliance. But there seems to be little appetite amongst them to prioritise the Karakol river valley between the Karakol pass and Suusamyrlar for any kind of action in terms of protected area creation or community-based conservation initiatives through local tourism. This project in particular has attempted to create awareness and action for eight years and will do so for another year, in 2023, before considering moving elsewhere, where the limited resources of this citizen science endeavour are better placed and have higher chances of succeeding.

Tasks for the expedition in 2023

In light of the above, tasks for the expedition and the local scientist in 2023 will be to:

1. Continue to evaluate and map the current status of snow leopard and prey populations in the Kyrgyz Ala-Too range, concentrating efforts in areas predicted to be good habitat suitability for both the snow leopard and its prey. In doing so, it will pay special attention to argali and yak for the reasons given above.
2. Communicate with ecotourism stakeholders and businesses in an attempt to facilitate actions between herders and local tour operators on the ground.
3. Continue to strengthen relationships with local partners NABU and the CCTG, and build relationships with other local stakeholders such as the Snow Leopard Conservancy, Foundation Ilbirs and other protected areas.
4. Assess other areas that the expedition could move to, should no progress towards conservation efforts and protected area or wildlife corridor creation be possible.

2.5. Literature cited

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Appendix I: Mammal sighting and call records of the 2022 expedition.

#	Species	Number of individuals	Cell	Record type	Date
1	Marmot	2	AI 19	Sighting	
2	Marmot	2	AI 18	Sighting, call	13.07.2022
3	Ibex	1	AH 20	Sighting	
4	Marmot	3	AE 19	Sighting	
5	Marmot	1	AE 21	Sighting	
6	Ibex	10	AE 21	Sighting	14.07.2022
7	Marmot	2	AE 19	Sighting	
8	Marmot	4	AF 19	Sighting, call	
9	Ibex	1	AF 21	Sighting	
10	Marmot	3	AE 17	Sighting	15.07.2022
11	Marmot	2	AG 18	Sighting	16.07.2022
12	Marmot	2	AG 19	Sighting	
13	Marmot	1	AG 17	Sighting	
14	Marmot	1	AF 17	Sighting	
15	Marmot	1	AF 16	Sighting	
16	Weasel	1	AF 16	Sighting	18.07.2022
17	Badger	1	AF 17	Sighting	
18	Ibex	24	AG 14, 15	Sighting	
19	Marmot	1	AG 17	Call	
20	Marmot	4	AG 16	Sighting, call	
21	Marmot	1	AM 16	Sighting	
22	Marmot	1	AM 16	Call	19.07.2022
23	Marmot	1	AI 16	Call	
24	Marmot	3	AK 16	Sighting	
25	Marmot	1	AI 18	Call	22.07.2022
26	Marmot	1	AI 19	Call	
27	Marmot	1	AI 18	Sighting	27.07.2022
28	Marmot	1	AI 19	Sighting	
29	Ibex	7	AE 21	Sighting	
30	Marmot	2	AE 18	Sighting	
31	Marmot	3	AE 19	Sighting	28.07.2022
32	Badger	1	AE 19	Sighting	
33	Marmot	1	AF 20	Sighting, call	
34	Stoat	1	AF 20	Sighting	
35	Marmot	1	AB 20	Call	
36	Marmot	4	AD 19	Call	
37	Marmot	1	AD 18	Sighting	29.07.2022
38	Snowcock	2	AD 18	Sighting	
39	Ibex	3	AB 19	Sighting	
40	Marmot	2	AF 17	Sighting	1.08.2022
41	Stone marten	1	AF 16	Sighting	
42	Marmot	1	AJ 18	Call	
43	Marmot	4	AE 18	Sighting, call	
44	Marmot	3	AE 19	Sighting	2.08.2022
45	Marmot	2	AF 19	Sighting	
46	Marmot	2	AE 20	Sighting	
47	Marmot	1	AG 15	Sighting	4.08.2022
48	Marmot	1	AD 17	Sighting	5.08.2022
49	Marmot	1	AI 18	Sighting	10.08.2022
50	Marmot	3	AE 19	Sighting, call	11.08.2022
51	Marmot	2	AF 20	Sighting, call	
52	Marmot	1	AO 17	Sighting	12.08.2022
53	Ibex	2	AM 15	Sighting	

Appendix I (continued): Mammal sighting and call records of the 2022 expedition.

#	Species	Number of individuals	Cell	Record type	Date
54	Marmot	1	AM 16	Sighting	
55	Marmot	8	AK 16	Sighting, call	
56	Marmot	1	AG 16	Sighting	
57	Marmot	3	AI 16	Sighting	
58	Marmot	4	AF 17	Sighting	14.08.2022
59	Ibex	8	AF 16	Sighting	
60	Marmot	1	AD 16	Sighting	15.08.2022
61	Ibex	3	V 13	Sighting	
62	Ibex	1	AJ 18	Sighting	18.08.2022

Appendix II: Mammal and bird sign records of the 2022 expedition.

#	Species	Cell	Record type	Date
1	Ibex	AF 20	Scats	
2	Ibex	AF 20	Tracks	14.07.2022
3	Stone marten?	AF 20	Scats	
4	Marmot	AE 16	Scats	
5	Ibex	AE 15	Scats	15.07.2022
6	Snowcock?	AE 15	Scats	
7	Marmot	AF 17	Scats	
8	Snow leopard?		Scats	
9	Badger	AF 16	Scats	18.07.2022
10	Badger	AG 15	Scats	
11	Ibex	AM 14	Scats	19.07.2022
12	Ibex	AC 16	Scats	
13	Marmot?	AC 16	Track	20.07.2022
14	Ibex	AF 21	Track	
15	Snow leopard		Scats, tracks	21.07.2022
16	Ibex	AE 21	Scats, tracks	
17	Ibex	AC 20	Scats, tracks	
18	Snow leopard?		Scats, tracks	
19	Marmot	AD 20	Scats	
20	Snow leopard?		Scats	29.07.2022
21	Ibex	AB 20	Scats, tracks	
22	Snowcock	AA 20	Scats	
23	Ibex	AA 20	Scats, tracks	
24	Snow leopard?		Scats	
25	Snow leopard?		Scats	
26	Ibex	AE 16	Scats	1.08.2022
27	Ibex	AF 16	Scats	
28	Snowcock	AE 15, 16, 17	Scats	
29	Marmot	AJ 18	Scats	2.08.2022
30	Ibex	AJ 18	Tracks	
31	Ibex	AF 21	Tracks	
32	Ibex	Out of ridge	Scats, tracks	
33	Snowcock	Out of ridge	Scats, tracks	3.08.2022
34	Ibex	AF 15	Scats	
35	Ibex	AG 16	Scats	4.08.2022
36	Ibex	AC 16	Tracks	5.08.2022
37	Wolf	AH 18	Scats	
38	Ibex	AI 20	Tracks	10.08.2022
39	Badger	AF 20	Scats	
40	Wolf	AF 20	Scats	11.08.2022

Appendix II (continued): Mammal and bird sign records of the 2022 expedition.

#	Species	Cell	Record type	Date
41	Fox?	AO 15	Scats	
42	Ibex	AL 14	Scats, tracks	
43	Snow leopard?		Tracks	12.08.2022
44	Ibex	AM 14	Tracks	
45	Ibex	AH 15	Tracks	
46	Snow leopard?		Tracks	14.08.2022
47	Snow leopard?		Scats	
48	Snow leopard?		Tracks	15.08.2022
49	Ibex	AE 15, 16	Scats, tracks	
50	Ibex	AC 16	Tracks	
51	Wolf	AA 20	Scats	16.08.2022
52	Ibex	AA 20	Tracks	
53	Snowcock	Z 17	Scats	
54	Ibex	Z 16	Tracks	
55	Snowcock	Z 16	Scats	17.08.2022
56	Snow leopard?		Tracks	
57	Ibex	V14	Scats, tracks	
58	Ibex	V 13	Scats, tracks	
59	Snowcock	AJ 19	Scats	
60	Ibex	AJ 19	Scats	18.08.2022
61	Snowcock	AF 15	Scats	
62	Ibex	AF 15	Scats, tracks	

Appendix III: Expedition reports, publications, diary & further information

Project updates, reports and publications:

<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

All expedition reports, including this and previous expedition reports:

<https://www.biosphere-expeditions.org/reports>

Expedition diary/blog:

<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/tien-shan-2019/> and

<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/tien-shan-2020/>

Expedition details, background, pictures, videos, etc.

<https://www.biosphere-expeditions.org/tienshan>